

Devyaṃata, sirāmarmaparijñāna ekonāśītipāṭalaḥ, edition.

N f80v, line 2; M f48r, line 4; W f52r, line 6.

79.1 sirā vaṃśo 'nuvaṃśāś ca marmopamarmasandhayaḥ
vāstumadhye prayatnena jñātvā hy etān vivarjayet

W f52v

79.2 yā tu karṇāyatā rekhā sirānāmnīti sā smṛtā
sirālakṣaṇam ākhyātāṃ vaṃśalakṣaṇam ucyate

79.3 vāruṇādityagaṃ sūtram māhendraśuragaṃ tathā
ṭṛtīyaṃ vaṃśasūtram syāt puṣpadantāc ca satyagam

79.4 yamāc ca somago vaṃśaḥ carakād adhamāgataḥ
gandharvāc ca tathā cānyo bhalvāṭapadamadhyagaḥ

79.5 ādityayamayor madhye yamavarūṇayos tathā
varūṇasomayoś caiva somaādityayoḥ punaḥ

M f48v

79.6 samāḥ karṇāyatā rekhāś catasraḥ saṃvyavasthitāḥ
anuvaṃśāḥ samākhyātā rekhānyāḥ sandhayaḥ smṛtāḥ

79.7 rekhānāṃ ye tu saṃpātāḥ marmāṇi tāni vāstutaḥ
padamadhyasthitāni syur upamarmāṇi tāni tu

Ω = NM(→W)

N is illegible at 79.3b

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|-------------------------------|--|
| 1a sirā] em.; śiro NM | 1b marmopamarma] N; marmmaupamarmma M |
| 3c vaṃśa] N; vaśa M | 4a yamāc] em.; yammāc N; yakṣmāc M |
| • vaṃśaḥ] N; vaṃśa M | 4b carakād] M; [***] N |
| 4c gandharvāc] N; gandharvā M | • tathā cānyo] em.; tathācānye N; tathānye M |
| 5b varūṇayos] N; varūṇayo M | 5c somayoś] N; somayo M |
| 6a samāḥ] em.; samā NM | 6b catasraḥ] N; catasra M |
| 6c anuvaṃśāḥ] M; anuvaṃśā N | 6d rekhānyāḥ] em.; rekhānyā NM |
| • smṛtāḥ] M; smṛtaḥ N | 7a ye] N; re M |
| | 7b vāstutaḥ] N; vastutaḥ M |

- 79.8 mūrdhani vadane nābhau stanayor hṛdaye tathā
mahāmarmāṇi cōktāni vāstudehe tu lakṣayet
- 79.9 padaṣoḍaśamo bhāgaḥ sirāpramāṇam ucyate W f53r
vaṃśādiṣu krameṇaiva pramāṇam procyate 'dhunā
- 79.10 aṣṭamo daśamo bhāgo bhāgo dvādaśamas tathā
padaṣoḍaśamo 'yaṃ ca bhāgo dvādaśamaḥ punaḥ
- 79.11 vaṃśādīnāṃ krameṇaiva pramāṇam samudāhṛtam
sthūlapramāṇam ākhyātam sūkṣmam pramāṇam ucyate
- 79.12 yavāṣṭakapramāṇam tu ekaikaṃ hrāsayed yavam
vaṃśādīnāṃ pramāṇam syāt mahāmarmasya cādhimam
- 79.13 īśāgnipitaro rogas trīśūleṣu vyavasthitāḥ
ṣaṭkoṇo vajra evoktāś catuṣkoṇeṣu saṃsthitāḥ
- 79.14 āpavatsā ca sāvitṛī indrajayo guhas tathā
īśānādiṣu koṇeṣu catuṣkāḥ saṃvyavasthitāḥ

$\Omega = NM(\rightarrow W)$

8a mūrdhani] N; mūrdhnani M • vadane] N; vedane M

8b stanayor] em.; tanayo NM 8c marmāṇi] N; sammāṇi M

9a ṣoḍaśamo bhāgaḥ] em.; śoḍasamobhāgaḥ N ṣoḍaśamobhāga M;

9b pramāṇam] conj. sumāram N; sumāṇam M 10ab bhāgo bhāgo] M; bhāgo N

10c ṣoḍaśamo] em.; śoḍaśamo N; śoḍaśamo M

12d marmasya cādhimam] em.; marmasyacādimaṃ N; marmmāśyacādimaṃ M

13a pitaro rogas] M; pitarogas N 13c koṇo] N; koṇa M

14b guhas] N; guhās M 14d catuṣkāḥ] em.; catuṣko NM

79.15 stambhakūṭyādīmadhye tu eṣāṃ madhye tu nākramet
sirādikramaṇe doṣān kathayāmi viśeṣataḥ

79.16 stambhakūṭyādīmadhyena sirāmadhye yadākramet
ūrdhvago dhananāśāś ca maraṇāś ca kulakṣayam

M f49r

79.17 ākrānte vaṃśamadye tu svāmīno maraṇaṃ dhruvam
pīḍite vānuvaṃśe tu vatsarāt pīḍanād bhayam

79.18 marmamadye samākrānte svāmīnaḥ kulasaṃkṣayam
upamarme samākrānte svāmīno rugbhayaṃ bhavet

79.19 sandhimadye samākrānte ūrdhvago kalahaḥ sadā
mitranāśo 'rthahānīś ca svāmīno bhavate dhruvam

N f81r

W f 53v

79.20 mahāmarmasya madhye tu stambhādīnāṃ yadākramet
svāmīno maraṇaṃ vidyād arthanāśaṃ kulakṣayam

79.21 triśūle garbhanāśaḥ syāt śatke ca vahyavairatā
vidyād vidyakramaṇaiva catuṣke vāhanakṣayaḥ

$\Omega = NM(\rightarrow W)$

15ab madhye tu eṣāṃ madhye tu nākramet] N; madhyetunākramet M

15c kramaṇe] N; krame M • doṣān] N; doṣāḥ M

16d maraṇāś ca] N; marasvā M 18a marmamadye] N; marmmadye M

18b svāmīnaḥ] N; svāmīno M • kula] N; tula M 18d rug] N; gurug M

19b sadā] N; sadāḥ M 19d bhavate] N; bhave M

20b stambhādīnāṃ] N; stambhādīnā M 20d nāśaṃ] N; nāśaḥ M

21a tri] N; ṭṛ M 21b vairatā] N; voratā M

21d catuṣke] conj.; catuṣko NM

79.22 tasmāt stambhādīmadhye tu madhyam eṣāṃ tu nākramet
vihāya madhyame teṣāṃ dravyāṇi saṃniveśayet

79.23 sirādi brahmasthānāni dvāramadhyāni tāni tu
marmavedhaṃ pṛthak tv eṣu marmasthāneṣu kathyate

79.24 yena dravyeṇa ye doṣā marmasampīḍite bhavet
tad dravyaṃ ca tathā doṣāḥ krameṇa procyate 'dhunā

79.25 bhittivistāramadhyena marmadvāreṇa pīḍite
dāridryaṃ svāmīno vidyāt tathā ca kulasamkṣayam

79.26 stambhena maraṇaṃ vidyāt tulayā strīvadho dhruvam
saṃgrahair bandhanāśas tu jayantyā ca ‡ ‡ vadham

M f49v

79.27 sandhipālaiḥ suhṛnnāśo nāgadantaiḥ suhṛdvadhaḥ
ṣaḍdārūṇy avalokāni dvāragavākṣakāni ca

79.28 marmamadhyaniviṣṭāni kurvanti dhanasaṃkṣayam
tulayā dvāradravyeṇa dvāramadhyena vā tathā

W f54r

Ω = NM(→W)

22c teṣāṃ] N; teṣā M

23b madhyāni] N; madhyani M

23c vedhaṃ] em.; vedha NM

24b sampīḍite] N; saṃpīḍito M

24c tad dravyaṃ] N; tadravyaṅ M • tathā doṣāḥ] em.; tathādoṣā N; kramedoṣā M

24d krameṇa procyate 'dhunā] N; kramekaṃprocyatedhunā M

26c saṃgrahair] N; saṃgraher M

26d jayantyā] N; jayatyā M

• ‡ ‡/; strasā M; [**] N

27b dantaiḥ] M; dantai N

27c dārūṇy] em.; dāruṇy NM

28a niviṣṭhāni] M; viriṣṭhāni N

28c tulayā] M; kulayā N

- 79.29 stambhena nāgadantena yadi marma prapīḍitam
rogās tasmin pravardhante dhananāśaḥ kulakṣayaḥ
- 79.30 gajapīḍā bhaved asmin putrāṇaṃ ca prapīḍanam
ṣaḍdārukasya madhye tu marmavedhas tu tatphalam
- 79.31 śapyāt tu vaṃśavinyastā nihanyāt svāminaḥ kulam
nāgadantena saṃsiddhā sarvadāsākṣamāvahā
- 79.32 nāgadantena vā viddhā stambhavātāyanena vā
bhartuḥ śastrabhayaṃ vidyāt taskarād vā mahābhayam
- 79.33 gṛhamadhye kṛte dvāre mṛtyuḥ syād dravyasaṃkṣayaḥ
kalahaś ca tathā śoko bhāryāduścāriṇī bhavet
- 79.34 dravyeṇaikatareṇāpi cet mahāmarma pīḍyate
kartuḥ sarvasvanāśaḥ syāt maraṇaṃ vā dhruvaṃ bhavet
- 79.35 yasminn aṅge bhaved vedho vāstudehe yathāsthite
tasminn aṅge bhaved duḥkhaṃ svāmīno nātra saṃśayaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

- 29a nāgadantena] N; nāgantena M 29c pravardhante] N; pravarttante M
30a bhaved asmin] em.; bhavetasmiṃ NM
30c dārukasya madhye] N; dārukasyadhye M 31a śapyāt tu] N; śatu M
• vinyastā] N; vinistā M 31b nihanyāt] N; hanyāt M
31c saṃsiddhā] N; saṃviddhā M 31d kṣamāvahā] M; kṣamāvahāḥ N
32b stambha] em.; stambho NM 33b mṛtyuḥ] N; mṛtyu M
33d duścāriṇī] N; daścāriṇī M
34c sarvasvanāśaḥ syāt] M; sarva[****] N
34d maraṇaṃ] N; maraṇa M 35a vedho] N vadho M

79.36 tasmād vai sarvayatnena marmavedhaṃ vivarjayet
ajñānān marmavedhaḥ syāj jñātvā hy etaṃ samārabhet

79.37 yat marma pīḍitaṃ bhadre tasya devaṃ pratarpayet
athavāghoradevaṃ tu śatenāṣṭottareṇa tu

W f54v

M f50r

79.38 sirādimarmavijñānaṃ vāstunaḥ samudāhṛtam
śalyoddhāraṃ viśeṣeṇa procyate śṛṇu sāmpratam

iti sirāmarmaparijñāna ekonāśītipaṭalaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

36a yatnena] N; yatnaiva M 36c ajñānān] em.; ajñānāt NM

36d jñātvā hy etaṃ samārabhet] em.; jñātvāhyesaṃsamārabhet N;

jñānātmarmmavedhaḥrabhet M 38b vāstunaḥ] N; vāstuta M

38c śalyoddhāraṃ] em.; śalyoddhāra N; śaloddhāraṃ M

after 38 iti sirāmarmaparijñāna ekonāśītipaṭalaḥ] em.;

itiśirāmarmaparijñānapaṭalaḥ N; itidevyāmatesirāmarmaparijñānekonāśītipaṭalaḥ M